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Conflict and Community Development in Nigeria: A Study of Rural Communities in the Niger Delta Area

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined conflict and community development in selected rural communities in the Niger Delta area. The paper further examines among others the relationship between conflict and community development and the implication of these conflicts on community development. The study adopted both primary and secondary data. Primary data includes questionnaires and interview while secondary data includes texts books, academic journals, and the internet. The theoretical framework used in this study is the Frustration-Aggression theory in conflict analysis. It was discovered amongst others that, conflicts in the selected communities were characterized by greed, self-centeredness, economic disequilibrium, political affiliation, and boundary disputes leading to destruction of properties, displacement and most often death and do not engender community development in rural communities in the Niger Delta region. Violent conflict has an adverse effect on the environment and economy of these rural communities and do not also engender community development. The paper recommends among others that the government should strengthen her security agents to be able to combat criminal activities while adopting dialogue and negotiation to resolve these conflicts. The state government should also spell out modalities for appointing leaders and award of chieftaincy titles that are conflict-free. Also, the government should ensure good governance based on accountability, transparency and the pursuit of public good or the common interest is most likely to end all forms of agitations that are leading to violence.

Keywords: Conflict, Community, Development, Niger Delta

I. INTRODUCTION

The struggle of the Niger Delta people in Nigeria has been a concern since the discovery of oil in Oloibiri, Bayelsa state by Shell-BP in 1956, and in Ogoni, Rivers state in 1957 (The Gobar Foundation, 2016). Despite the fact that the Niger Delta holds the secrete to Nigeria's abundant crude oil export, accounting for about 90% of Nigeria's revenue, (Akpan & Akpabio, 2009), local communities in the Niger Delta remain poor. Osuoka, (2003) found that resorting to conflicts by the Niger Delta people has become the only viable way of expressing grievances by the oil rich communities since most of the youths are unemployed, opportunity cost of fighting becomes extremely low, which further exacerbates the already deteriorating conditions.

Although the Niger Delta locals claim that the government has not done enough in bringing this situation under control (Omotola, 2007), the Nigerian government has not been completely unresponsive to their demands. For example, Worldbank (2009) reports that several measures have been taken by the government to reduce the conflict, with the establishments of bodies such as the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) in 1999, Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission (OMPADEC) in 1992, Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs (MNDA) in 2008 and the amnesty program by President Yar'Adua in 2009, which were all created as a move to encourage economic and social development and reduce the conflict in the regions (John, 2011). However, adequate effort has not been made in trying to combat conflict using community development measures. This may be as a

result of ignorance of the theoretical stance on the effect of underdevelopment on conflict. It is in this light; this paper investigates conflicts and community development in the Niger Delta with focus on rural communities from 2003 - 2023. It will examine the relationship between conflict and community development, impact of conflict on the environment and the implications of conflict on community development.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Frustration-Aggression theory which the study relied upon was developed in 1939 by John Dollard and his team research associates, but it was being expanded and modified by other scholars such as Leonard Berkowitz (1962) and Aubrey Yates (1962) which distinctly appears to be the common explanation for violent behaviour stemming from the inability to fulfil needs. Theorists that rely on this explanation use the psychological theories of behaviour and motivation, as well as frustration and aggression (Faleti, in Best, 2006).

It is indicative that attempts made to explain aggression, scholars often identify the difference(s) between what people feel they want or deserve to what they actually want to get (Iyoboyi, 2014) and of course the difference between “expected need satisfaction” and “the actual need satisfaction” (Davies in Ray & Esteban, 2017). This means that, where expectation does not tally (meet) attainment, there is then the tendency for people (including Ethnic Nationalities) to confront those they hold responsible for frustrating their ambitions, etc. To this end, Ted Robert Gur’s relative deprivation thesis becomes pivotal. Gur have argued that the greater the dependency, however marginal, between what is sought and what seem attainable, the greater will be the chances that anger and violence will result” (Faleti, in Best, 2006).

The central theme of the frustration-aggression theory according to Okolo (n.d) is that aggression is not just restricted exclusively to as a natural reaction or instinct as the realistic and the biological schools or theorists assume, but much more importantly, the theory (Frustration-Aggression) emphasizes on the outcome of frustration and that in a situation where the legitimate desires of an individual is denied either directly or by the indirect consequence of the way of society is structured, the feeling of disappointment may lead such a person or group of persons to exert/express his anger through violence that will be directed at those he/she and/or they perceived or holds responsible or people who are directly or indirectly related to them. He noted that where there is an apparent feeling of frustration among a wide array of the population of a given society and the feeling expressed is such that people are getting far less than they deserve, the most advisable thing that political leaders are encouraged to do is to find out what the expectations of such individuals and groups are and to urgently seek ways of negotiating with them. This needed to be the approach in the violent conflictual situation in the Niger Delta. But in most cases, however, those in charges or in position of authority believe that giving in to public demands or entering into negotiations is a sign of weakness on the part of Government. In my mind, and to those who share the same views with me, the fact that an official of government visits the people / an area means so much to such a group of people, and this can in no small measure inform such a people for a better relation.

However, Iyoboyi (2014) revealed that a common and clear example of the manner in which frustration leads to aggression is vividly shown in the ongoing crises in the Nigeria’s Niger Delta region. Clearly, after waiting patiently and peacefully agitating for what the various people of the region considered as a fair share of the oil wealth that is relentlessly exploited from the region (land), Youths and other stakeholders now explored other means, take law into their own hands by kidnapping oil workers from very fat ransoms; vandalizing oil pipelines and of course generally engaging themselves in the creation of problems for those they collectively think and believe are directly or indirectly responsible for their manifest predicaments. The above clearly is an indication of why ethnic groups in the region perceive others as a stumbling block to their progress, and therefore, the resultant effects are demonstrated in the several violent conflictual situations we have had to contend with in area.

III. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Concept of Conflict

Conflict, as defined by numerous experts, is the result of a struggle between two or more parties over ideals and claims to status, power, and valuable resources, with the intention of neutralizing, harming, or eliminating their adversaries (Abass, 2018). Otite et al. (2006) and Okafor (2017) also view conflict as a state of disagreement or confrontation between multiple parties vying for possession or control of scarce and highly coveted resources. Akpan and Akpabio (2019) describes conflict as an escalated competition between groups at any system level, each striving to outperform the others. Conflicts manifest as disagreements, arguments, fights, and even wars, occurring among individuals, communities, and nations. In any society, the allocation of wealth, influence, and reputation rarely sees unanimous agreement due to the diverse interests of different groups and individuals, leading to inevitable conflicts between their respective goals. Deprived groups and individuals, seeking to improve their share of available resources and power or challenge prevailing norms, attitudes, or ideologies, often trigger conflicts (Iyoboyi, 2014).

Otite et al (2006) noted that the dynamics of conflict arise from the inherent diversity in human interests and aspirations. They contended that as long as different groups and individuals vie for their distinct objectives within a limited pool of resources and opportunities, conflicts will continue to emerge, shaping the interactions and outcomes in various social contexts. Conflict is commonly understood as a state of incompatibility in thoughts or goals, where parties hold conflicting attitudes or values, leading to tension and a failure to reach a peaceful agreement or compromise. This inability to find common ground may prompt one or both parties to resort to violence in pursuit of self-oriented objectives. Communal conflict, as defined by Sixtus and Nafiasah (2019), arises when individuals or groups have competing interests over valuable and scarce resources, both tangible and intangible. Such conflicts can occur within a community (intra-group) or between different communities (inter-group). The existence of shared bonds or commonalities across groups often exacerbates the intensity of the competition. Communal conflicts are a result of complex social interactions, including issues of control, participation, production, and consumption within a society. Depending on the degree of escalation, managing these conflicts can become challenging (Sixtus and Nafiasah, 2019). In rural areas in Nigeria, conflicts erupted or organized around ethnic divide and most of the time over grazing areas and over cattle rustlings amongst pastoral people; also, there are dispute over cultivable land amongst farmers within the same ethnic group and also between ethnic groups. Pastoralist Fulani ethnic group in Nigeria most of the time had conflict with rural farmers over grazing lands which later escalate into ethnic armed conflict between the farmers and the grazers. Most of these rural conflicts over land and cattle have been going on over a long period of time and is happening silently, unreported to the authorities concern, unless large scale killing and destructions takes place and the government intervenes. According to Adedeji (2019), violent ethnic conflict is a sign of a weak, fragile state or state deeply involved in ancient ethnic loyalty. In this awkward situation, states act with bias mind to favour a particular ethnic group or community, and behaviour such as preferential treatment spark up violent ethnic conflict. Violent ethnic conflict can take different types or forms from collective ethnic violence which is perpetrated by a group or ethnic group against another. Communal clashes have persistently occurred across various regions, resulting in significant destruction of infrastructure, loss of human lives, and adverse effects on the nation's productivity (Sixtus and Nafiasah, 2019). Notably, Northern Nigeria has witnessed a higher frequency of community conflicts compared to other parts of the country, affecting states like Jos, Benue, Nasarawa, Bauchi, Adamawa, Kaduna, Taraba, and Kogi (Abass 2017). As a consequence, these conflicts have rendered affected communities unstable, hazardous, and inhospitable, hindering successful social interactions and economic activities (Ray and Esteban, 2017).

Concept of Community Development

It appears that there is no consensus on the meaning and goals of community development. Hence, the diversity of definitions. Ekong in Anikeze (2014) sees community development as any action in a locality by any agency with the primary intention of bringing some benefits to such locality. This implies that community development is a movement designed to promote better living for the whole

community with active participation and on the initiative of the community. Premium Times (2015) holds a similar view and affirms that community development is an educational process; it is something of the spirit more than something material. It must reach into deep cultural pattern of people, examining them and testing them as principle of faith. It is not a temporary, physical construction. It is a building within the heart and mind of men not a recreation centre in the middle of a field. Okafor (2017) defined community development as efforts provided for advancement of communities, hesitated that the major emphasis of the concept was upon those activities which aim at prorating the improvement of the basic condition of the community's non material need.

This implies that community development is aimed at community action where community action is used as a phenomenon that recommends that community members resolve their problems by directly participating in development activities. Anikeze (2014) posited that community development as a process of social action in which people took action to meet those needs with maximum reliance on their own initiative and resources, supplemented with assistance in any government and non-governmental organization. He identifies some underlying philosophy and principles of community development since community development organized self-help to improve themselves through democracy, participation, and self-direction. In Nigeria, like in most developing countries, the governmental authority usually involved in community development is the local government because it is the closest level of government to the people. The central focus is that the efforts of the community themselves must, of necessity, be united with that of any other agency, whether governmental or non-governmental, to improve the living conditions of the communities. This calls for the realisation on the part communities that they have to make some efforts to uplift their living conditions.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Niger Delta is located in the Southern part of Nigeria, mainly populated by the Ijaw ethnic nationality. Spreading over a total landmass of about 70,000 square kilometres, the region is inhabited by an estimated population of 42 million Nigerians in over 500 communities (Alagoa, 2004). The paper adopted both primary and secondary data while Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine a sample of 400 respondents in a population of 42,112,908. The purposive sampling technique was used to select communities that have recorded conflicts. For the purpose of clarity, two communities are taken from each state of the Niger Delta. The communities include: Apumiri and Ariaria (Abia State), Ukanafun and Esit-Eket (Akwa Ibom State), Nembe Ogbolomabiri and Nembe Bassambiri (Bayelsa State), Usumutong and Ediba (Cross River State), Okere Urhobo and Okere Itsekiri (Delta State), Sabon Gida-Ora and Uhonmora-Ora (Edo State), Akuma and Ihodimeze (Imo), Ujugbere and Ikare-Akoko (Ondo State), and Okrika and Eleme (Rivers State).

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1: Methodological Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency	Percentage
Number of questionnaires administered	400	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	50	12%
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	350	88%

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above reveal that out of the 400 questionnaires administered to respondents, 50 making 12% of the questionnaires were not returned while 350 were successfully completed and valid for proper analysis. The response rate is 88% which is good for the study.

Table 2: Social and Demographic Background of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency (F)	Percentages (%)
Age bracket	18 – 40	230	66
	41 – 60	120	34
	Total	350	100
Gender distribution	Male	200	57
	Female	150	43
	Total	350	100
Education	SSCE/ND/NCE	150	43
	HND/BA/B.Sc/PGD	120	34
	MBA/MPA/M.Sc/Ph.D	80	23
	Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 2 above shows that 230 respondents representing 66% are within the age bracket of 18-40 years while 120 (34%) are within the age bracket of 41-60 years. This indicates that stakeholders are abreast with the issues under investigation. Also, the table above also shows that 200 questionnaires representing 57% were administered to male while 150 questionnaires with 43% were female. This reveals that the respondents who attended to the questionnaires are mainly males. Notwithstanding, responses from both genders are analysed for a valid judgement. Finally, the table above depicts that 150 (43%) have SSCE/ND/NCE; 120 (34%) respondents possess HND/BA/B.SC/PGD while 80 respondents representing 23% are holders of MBA/MPA/M.SC/Ph.D. This shows that the respondents are dominated by different levels of graduates with various certificate holders. This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge about the impact of conflict on community development in the Niger Delta.

Table 3: What is the relationship between conflict and community development?

Computation of the response rate on the relationship between conflict and community development.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Conflict engender criminality and increases that level of poverty in community development.	180 (51%)	150 (43%)	15 (4.3%)	5 (1.4%)	350 (100%)
Conflict institutes inter communal and inter communal violence against dwellers and their property in community development.	200 (57%)	100 (29%)	30 (9%)	20 (5%)	350 (100%)
Conflict has not enhanced socio-economic activities in community development.	150 (43%)	120 (34%)	50 (14%)	30 (9%)	350 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

From table 3 in response to item one, respondents affirmed that conflict engender criminality and increases that level of poverty in community development. This is agreed by 330 respondents representing 94% of the 350 respondents. The second item reveals that 300 respondents agreed that conflict institutes inter communal and inter communal violence against dwellers and their property in community development while, the last item got similar approval as 270 of the 350 respondents making 77% agreed that conflict has not enhanced socio-economic activities in community development. This implies that there is a relationship between conflict and community development.

**Table 5: What is the implication of these communal crises on community development?
Computation of responses on the implication of communal crises on community development**

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Boundary disputes between and among communities have led to communal crises in community development.	180 (51%)	150 (44%)	15 (4%)	5 (1%)	350 (100%)
Issues of leadership tussle and chieftaincy titles have contributed largely to communal crises in community development in the Niger Delta.	200 (57%)	100 (29%)	30 (9%)	20 (5%)	350 (100%)
Herdsmen/Farmers conflicts has resulted to hindered community development in the Niger Delta.	150 (43%)	120 (34%)	50 (14%)	30 (9%)	350 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

From table 5 in response to item one, respondents affirmed that boundary disputes between and among communities have led to communal crises in community development. This is accounted for by the high number of 330 respondents representing 95%. Similarly, it was agreed for the second item that issues of leadership tussle and chieftaincy titles have contributed largely to communal crises in community development in the Niger Delta. This is also confirmed by 300 respondents of 86% of the 350 respondents. In addition, it was agreed for the last item that herdsmen/Farmers conflicts has resulted to hindered community development in the Niger Delta. This is also confirmed by 270 respondents representing 77% of the 350 participants.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between conflict and community development: Data analysis affirmed that conflict engender criminality and increases that level of poverty in community development. This is agreed by 330 respondents representing 94% of the 350 respondents. The second item reveals that 300 respondents agreed that conflict institutes inter communal and inter communal violence against dwellers and their property in community development while, the last item got similar approval as 270 of the 350 respondents making 77% agreed that conflict has not enhanced socio-economic activities in community development. In line with this position, an interviewee reveals that:

During the period, a lot of clashes have taken place in my state. For instance, there was a case of criminal violence in Ethiope East, Ughelli North and Udu LGAs. Criminality during the period was driven largely by kidnapping, robbery, arms proliferation and clashes between security forces and hoodlums. In January, for instance, gunmen reportedly killed three policemen and stole their weapons in Ekiugbo town, Ughelli North LGA. In March, robbers reportedly attacked two banks, a petrol station and a restaurant, and killed four persons in Issele-Uku town, Aniocha LGA. In July, a soldier and two robbers were reportedly killed in a gun battle in Tuomo community, Burutu LGA. All happened in 2021 (J. Ejiro, personal communication, August 2, 2024).

Also, another respondent reveals that:

Criminality in Rivers State during the year related mainly to sea robbery/piracy, kidnapping and clashes between security operatives and hoodlums. In February, for example, pirates reportedly hijacked a passenger boat and abducted 12 persons along the waterways in Bonny LGA. In April, gunmen reportedly killed six youths in Uegwere community, Khana LGA. (T. Barinua, personal communication, August 5, 2024).

In the light of the above, community development becomes a mirage since its success is predicated on social cohesion or unity (Walker, 2016). The generation of funds is made easy when community members share common goals and destiny, but social disintegration undermines this. The most evident effect is the emerging trend where community members cannot sit together to plan their development, due to community factions and the underlying hatred. Communities in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria have witnessed so many cases of armed conflict in the past. According to Aceddata (2016), there has been more than 500 cases of armed conflict for Bayelsa, Delta, and Rivers state during the period under study. These cases include, wanton destruction of community properties, killing of innocent people, destruction of farmlands, destruction of crude oil pipelines, bombing of government buildings, killing of oil workers and other violent acts (Kim and Conceicao, 2010). With these cases of armed conflict in many communities in the Niger Delta, it can be ascertained that conflict is the reason behind the underdevelopment in the region (Okafor, 2017). In which case, community development cannot thrive in the face of violent conflict.

Walker (2016) also reported similar findings, arguing that conflict has adverse effects on economic development. These periods were encumbered with a total or partial destruction of the communities involved (Okolo, n.d). The scholar argued that residential buildings, schools, hotels and bridges were among the properties destroyed. He noted that the insecurity associated with conflicts also scares contractors away from project sites, thus leading to the abandonment of community development projects. The destruction and displacements that follow conflicts, particularly intra-communal conflicts, have created social dislocation and the subsequent destruction of the social structure of affected communities. This impedes community development, as the self-help approach to community development is a major strategy for community development in the region. While there are many factors that could cause conflict, many empirical studies find that poor economic performance is associated with higher incidence of conflict (Kim and Conceicao, 2010). The foregoing discussion therefore revealed that conflict is characterized by the state of poverty leading to destruction of property, displacement and most often death. This indicates that conflict do not engender community development in rural communities in the Niger Delta region.

The implication of communal crises on community development: Respondents affirmed that boundary disputes between and among communities have led to communal crises in community development. This is accounted for by the high number of 330 respondents representing 95%. Similarly, it was agreed for the second item that issues of leadership tussle and chieftaincy titles have contributed largely to communal crises in community development in the Niger Delta. This is also confirmed by 300 respondents of 86% of the 350 respondents. In addition, it was agreed for the last item that herdsmen/Farmers conflicts have resulted to hindered community development in the Niger Delta. This is also confirmed by 270 respondents representing 77% of the 350 participants.

In consonant with the above, an interviewee notes that:

Several incidents of communal violence were reported in the State during the year, driven primarily by communal land disputes and the herder-farmer conflict. In February, for example, three farmers were reportedly killed and farmlands burned during a clash between farmers and herders in Ugo community, Orhionmwon LGA. In March, three residents were reportedly killed during a fight over a land dispute between Sabon Gida-Ora and Uhonmora-Ora communities in Owan West LGA. In August, a resident was reportedly killed and houses and livestock destroyed during clashes over a land dispute between the Ijaw and Bini ethnic groups in Ikoro and Obazuwa communities, Ovia North East LGA. (O. Osaze, personal communication, August 19, 2024).

Another interviewee reveals that:

Communal violence in Ondo State during the period was driven mainly by leadership tussle and the herder-farmer conflict. In February, for example, three persons were reportedly killed during a clash between farmers and herders in Ijugbere community, Owo LGA. In May, two residents were reportedly killed during a clash between two factions of youths supporting

two traditional chiefs over a chieftaincy tussle in Ikare-Akoko community, Akoko North East LGA. (O. Adebayo, personal communication, August 23, 2024).

Secondary data revealed that communal crises have a lot of effects on community development just like a sword with two sharp edges. In the words of Aja (2019), the common sense understanding of conflict is in the negative. It is a setback. It is disintegrative. Truly, conflict assumes this form, but not always. Adedeji (2019) averred that from the social reality perspective, conflict can lead to positive developments for the individuals, groups and the society as a whole. So, conflict can be a corrective measure or warning. According to Tamuno (1999), conflict can be development driven. Yet, whether conflict is in the negative or positive, it cannot be left alone. Okafor (2017) alerts Rivers State about Ahoada West that crisis looms in Aka-Olu community as chief and other prominent men in the community embezzled scholarship fund and converted community funds meant for compensation into their personal pockets. This report proves that the money already generated by Aka-Olu citizens and planned to empower the indigenous youth for skills acquisition programme has been embezzled by their chief and others to the detriment of the others. This attitude in effect is negative to the concepts of community development.

Ibaba (2009) opined that reoccurrence of crises have therefore weakened the social relationship that existed among the people and caused mutual suspicion instead of the spirit of cooperation among them. He alerted the spirit of development among individuals will be stronger when they are investing in property that belongs to them than those rented. He argued that this is because the people hope to reap the benefits of their investments and not think that their landlords live at their expenses. Iyoboyi (2014) pointed out that communal violence caused several fatalities in the State in 2021, driven mainly by land and boundary disputes. In January, for instance, three persons were reportedly killed and four others abducted during a clash over a boundary dispute between Nkari community in Ini LGA, Akwa Ibom State and Usaka Ukwu community in Ikwuano LGA, Abia State. In April, seven persons were reportedly killed and a woman raped during a clash over a boundary dispute between Ikpanya community in Ibiono Ibom LGA, Akwa Ibom State and Ugbo community in Arochukwu LGA, Abia State. In June, two residents were reportedly killed during a clash between herders and farmers in Ikot Atasung community, Ikot Ekpene LGA.

More so, Aja (2019) noted that Communal violence was prevalent in the State during the year, especially in Ughelli North, Ughelli South, Udu, Warri South, and Isoko South LGAs. Communal conflict caused more than 40 fatalities during this period, driven mainly by land and boundary disputes, leadership tussles, as well as herder/farmer clashes. In January, for instance, 10 persons were reportedly killed and several houses destroyed during a clash over a longstanding land dispute between Igbide and Emede communities in Isoko South LGA. In March, a man and his two children were reportedly killed during a clash between herders and farmers in Abraka town, Ethiope East LGA. In April, four persons were reportedly killed during a clash over the ownership of a market between Iwhreko and Ekiugbo communities, Ughelli North LGA. Before the crises, Sixtus and Nafisah (2019) claimed the drop in community development is associated with the destruction during the crisis. However, what is found to be common is the same faith patterns of movement were meant to ensure safety of lives and property during the crisis period.

Adedeji (2019) opined that communities in the Niger Delta are seen as some of the backward areas in terms of literacy rate. He claimed that the low literacy rate is associated to poverty and lack of educational infrastructure. Chukwuemeka and Aghara (2010) averred that basic infrastructure such as health, water, schools and electricity has suffered either destruction or disruption in the development process. Series of violent clashes have caused untold economic, political and social havoc in the many rural communities in the Niger Delta Area, plus unbearable loss in human killing and injuries (Walker, 2016). The effects of conflict have therefore spread across all members of the community irrespective of individual occupations. He revealed that the aftermath of these crises was so great that people have to move from one activity to the other to overcome the difficult period. According to him, large proportion of the population is engaged in subsistence farming and it may be difficult for them to raise enough money to carter for theft needs especially the rehabilitation of their homes, payment of school

fees, health care etc contribute towards communal efforts. Crises in the Niger Delta have retarded and impeded development activities in the area. Abass (2018) faulted field infatuation on output of farmers during the crises years and past crises years reviewed that farm yield dropped during the crises periods and kept dwindling after the crises, because all efforts made to increase food production during and after the crises were greatly affected by the crises. Instead, available resources were channelled into rehabilitation and resettlement exercise than investment in agriculture and other business (Walker, 2016). Moreso, results from and during the period of any crisis could also have been responsible for a decline in development goal (Okolo, n.d).

Another area of implication according to Iyoboyi (2014) is that households' incomes were highly affected and therefore, their inability to create wealth, live better lives and contribute meaningfully to rural economy. The struggle to survive through subsistence becomes more important and paramount than any other form of intensive investment (Ibaba, 2009). Business activities, according to Premium Times (2015) have suffered major setbacks during the communal crises periods and these have negative and adverse effects on rural development activities and processes. They claimed that when businesses flourish, local government council generates incomes in the form of taxes and this revenue, if properly utilized enhance lives of the people. Many years of recurrent communal crises destabilized most businesses, which are major contributors as the revenue sources of individuals and the local government council would lead to loss of large share of revenues which would have been generated from communities (Okafor, 2017). This poor performance in human activities implies limited contributions toward community development.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that conflict characterizes criminal violence such as robbery, piracy, kidnapping and gang crimes such as cultism, leadership tussle, land acquisition and chieftaincy title struggle and this endangers community development. The implication of conflict on community development is mass poverty, death, destruction of economic property, relocation of socioeconomic facilities and businesses, destruction of the environment, and so on. The negative impact of violence on the environment and on human lives and property impedes the development of production capabilities, wealth creation and poverty reduction in community development. Violent conflicts have undermined the growth of local economies in a number of ways – loss of working hours, loss of productive labour through forced migration, pollution of fishing grounds and farmlands and the disruption of farming and fishing.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings above, the following recommendations are made:

1. The government should strengthen her security agents to be able to combat criminal activities and adopt dialogue and negotiation in conflict management. The state government should also spell out modalities for appointing leaders and award of chieftaincy titles that are conflict-free.
2. The grievances of all stakeholders in a conflict should be put into cognizance for the sake of community development. Particularly, those who the people have implicit confidence and regards for needed to be identified and realistically engaged in facilitating this process.

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